

Single-Fiber Single-Wavelength Bidirectional Digital Subcarrier Point-to-Multipoint Coherent Systems for Beyond 5G Transport

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Abstract We experimentally investigate on single-fiber bidirectional coherent transmission for next-generation mobile transport in Point-to-Multipoint (P2MP) architecture, using power optimization to improve the performance in the presence of fiber reflections and crosstalk. ©2025 The Author(s)

Introduction

Coherent technology is spreading towards the edge of the optical networks, to meet the increasing capacity and reach demands of metro and access segments. One of the most demanding applications in the near future is represented by next-generation mobile transport networks^{[1],[2]}. The advantages of using a single-fiber architecture in these networks, in addition to saving resources in the fiber infrastructure, are discussed in^[3]. In brief, single-fiber architectures could benefit future mobile transport networks by minimizing adverse effects on their critical constant time error budgets, a crucial aspect given the stringent timing and synchronization demands of these networks^[4]. Furthermore, to reduce hardware complexity and costs, a single-laser transceiver (TRX) architecture is preferred. Digital Subcarrier Multiplexing (DSCM) technology facilitates such single-fiber, single-laser bidirectional (BiDi) links as shown in^[3].

Previous works^{[3],[5]–[9]} report on investigations of single-fiber Point-to-Point (P2P) BiDi links, their inherent reflections, and strategies to mitigate them. The solution based on DSCM TRXs with single-laser architecture allows operation either at full-capacity, where interference from reflections can be admitted, or at half-capacity by interleaving the Digital Subcarriers (DSCs) in the frequency domain. This interleaving ensures no spectral overlap between the DSCs assigned to up- and down-stream, thus avoiding interference from reflections^[10]. In^{[3],[8]}, we analyzed both configurations in P2P links, showing the tolerance of

the half-capacity operation against reflections, and quantifying the performance penalty from reflections arising from operating at full-capacity.

In this work, we explore the value proposition of using DSCM in P2MP single-fiber networks. In this scenario, the interplay between reflections and noise that affects the performance becomes more complex than in a P2P link. Therefore, a more complex power optimization is required. Here, we present experimental measurements showing the performance gain obtained by properly selecting the transmitted power of each node in a single-fiber configuration, consisting of one HUB communicating with two LEAFs in full-capacity mode^[3], affected mainly by distributed fiber reflections^[8].

Experimental setup

We show the experimental setups in Fig. 1. A P2MP network is set, connecting two HUBs and two LEAFs in a filterless horseshoe architecture^[11]. The HUB 2 is used for protection. We show in Fig. 1(a) the single-fiber implementation, which is the focus of this work, and in Fig. 1(b) the dual-fiber approach, used as a reference.

The HUBs and LEAFs employ coherent real-time DSCM-based TRXs with single-laser architecture^[12]. The 100G-LEAFs' TRXs operate with 4 DSCs per direction. The 400G-HUBs' TRXs operate with 16 DSCs per direction, using 4 different DSCs to communicate with each LEAF. Note that 8 HUB's DSCs are unused in this setup, but still active to set the full-capacity operation, as the more general condition. Each DSC has a symbol

Fig. 1: Experimental setup of the P2MP single-wavelength bidirectional network (a) with single-fiber and (b) with dual-fiber.

Fig. 2: Optical spectrum at the receiver side of LEAF1 and HUB.

rate of ~ 3.75 Gbd, using DP-16QAM modulation, resulting in a net bit rate of 25 Gbps per DSC. More details about the TRXs can be found in^[13].

Each LEAF has two TRXs, termed A and B, operating at a different laser frequency: 194.0 THz and 194.1 THz, respectively. LEAF1-A and LEAF2-A communicate with HUB1, using the same laser frequency. LEAF1-B and LEAF2-B do the same with HUB2. Therefore, we have two independent groups of nodes, each operating bidirectionally with the same laser frequency. In the single-fiber case, the overlap of the spectra generates interference from the reflections of the signals traveling in the other direction, causing a performance penalty.

In both architectures shown in Fig. 1, we use optical splitters/combiners to perform the traffic distribution/aggregation. In the single-fiber option, we use optical circulators to route the transmitter (TX) and receiver (RX) signals to the end node. In the following, we focus our analysis only on the first group of nodes formed by HUB1, LEAF1-A, and LEAF2-A, which are now termed HUB (H1), LEAF1 (L1) and LEAF2 (L2), for simplicity. Three Variable Optical Attenuators (VOAs) are used to set the transmitted power of the TRXs, with an attenuation value of: A_H at HUB TX, A_{L1} at LEAF1 TX and A_{L2} at LEAF2 TX. The length of H1 \rightarrow L1 fiber segment is $d_1 = 20$ km, and the length of H1 \rightarrow L2 fiber segments is 35 km (composed of two fiber segments, of $d_1 = 20$ km and $d_2 = 15$ km, having a splitter/combiner in between).

In Fig. 2 we show the optical spectrum at the RX side of the HUB (red) and the LEAF1 (blue). Regarding the spectrum at the HUB RX, we can observe the DSCs coming from the LEAFs, and

some reflected DSCs transmitted by the HUB (the in-band reflections are not visible). We set A_{L1} and A_{L2} to values that provide a LEAFs spectrum with the same power at the HUB RX.

Results and discussion

In this Section we show the performance improvement achieved by optimizing the transmitted powers in each node of the considered P2MP network. We use the Q-factor (Q^2) as a performance metric. We set the maximum total transmitted power on the LEAFs' TRXs, and then control the actual launch power using the corresponding VOAs. In the HUB, we set a maximum total TX power 6 dB higher than that of the LEAFs, to have the same maximum TX power per subcarrier in the three nodes. Therefore, to have the same total launch power in all nodes, we should set: $A_{L1} = A_{L2}$ and A_H [dB] = A_{L1} [dB] + 6 [dB].

As a starting point, we present the results obtained with the dual-fiber implementation. The impact of reflections on this architecture is negligible. Therefore, transmission is only affected by intrinsic TRX noise (electrical and optical) and the crosstalk (XT) between LEAF1 and LEAF2 signals at the HUB RX. The system is optically unamplified; therefore, the in-line optical noise is absent. We verified that the fiber non-linearities are also marginal even with the maximum launched powers set. We set a fixed HUB launch power, corresponding to $A_H = 6$ dB. In the H1 \rightarrow L1 transmission, a constant $Q^2 = 10.6$ dB is measured irrespective of the A_{L1} and A_{L2} values, as expected in the absence of reflections and crosstalk. We observe the same for the H1 \rightarrow L2 transmission, measuring a constant $Q^2 = 10.3$ dB. The situation is different at the HUB site, receiving simultaneously from LEAF1 (L1 \rightarrow H1) and LEAF2 (L2 \rightarrow H1). In this scenario, there is a variable impact of XT that depends on the imbalance of received power from LEAF1 and LEAF2^[13]. This behavior is shown in Fig. 3(a). We can observe a bending in the Q^2 -contour plots of a given LEAF signal resulting from the variation of the other LEAF signal attenuation/power. In other words, given, for example, a fixed A_{L1} , we observe a degradation of the L1 \rightarrow H1 Q^2 as the power of LEAF2 increases (i.e.,

Fig. 3: Q-factor versus TX attenuations of the LEAFs, for different transmission cases and for a TX attenuation of the HUB of 6 dB.

Fig. 4: Minimum Q^2 among all the connections ($H1 \rightarrow L1$, $H1 \rightarrow L2$, $L1 \rightarrow H1$ and $L2 \rightarrow H1$) versus attenuation values at TX of HUB, LEAF1 and LEAF2

the value of A_{L2} decreases), which could only be attributable to XT in the analyzed setup.

We repeated the same experiment with the single-fiber implementation. In this setup, we expect to see both the impact of XT and reflections, for a fixed HUB transmitted power ($A_H = 6$ dB). In fact, as displayed in Fig. 3(b), for the $L1 \rightarrow H1$ and $L2 \rightarrow H1$ transmissions, there is a Q^2 degradation with respect to the results of dual-fiber in Fig. 3(a). This performance penalty is due to the extra losses added by the circulators and the interference from the reflected HUB signal. The kind of reflections present in the single-fiber setup are mainly distributed reflections generated in the fiber through the Rayleigh Back-Scattering (RBS) effect. We verified that the discrete reflections were negligible by observing the spectrum when turning off some DSCs. This is not the general case in a real network implementation, and a generalized analysis including discrete reflections is an open topic for further research extension.

Regarding the results for $H1 \rightarrow L1$ transmission, shown in dashed-lines in Fig. 3(c), we observe a small impact of reflections coming from the back-reflected LEAF1 signal. In contrast, for $H1 \rightarrow L2$ transmission, shown in solid-lines in Fig. 3(c), the impact of reflections is noticeable. This is because the signal from the HUB reaches LEAF2 with a smaller power than to LEAF1 after traveling a longer distance. While in the case without reflections (i.e., the dual-fiber) the $H1 \rightarrow L2$ performance is constant irrespective of the LEAF2 transmitted power, in the case of a single-fiber, Q^2 significantly varies as a function of A_{L2} . This fact shows that reflections play an important role in the performance of this system. Moreover, it shows the potential for a proper optimization of the transmitted power. Let us compare the trends of the dashed-curves of Fig. 3(b) (i.e., $L2 \rightarrow H1$ connection) and the solid-curves of Fig. 3(c) (i.e. $H1 \rightarrow L2$ connection), focusing only on the performance variation with respect to the transmitted power of LEAF2 (controlled by A_{L2}). We observe that the performance of the signal received by the HUB from LEAF2 increases as A_{L2} decreases. This is caused by an increase of the signal to intrinsic TRX noise ratio.

On the other hand, a reverse trend is observed in the performance of the signal received by LEAF2 from the HUB: the performance increases as A_{L2} increases, since in this case, the LEAF2 reflected signal power decreases. An A_{L2} that maximizes the minimum Q^2 of $H1 \rightarrow L2$ and $L2 \rightarrow H1$ together can be found, which is, for instance, $A_{L2} \sim 3$ dB for $A_{L1} = 3$ dB, and $A_{L2} \sim 5$ dB for $A_{L1} = 15$ dB.

A similar analysis can be performed for the four connections: $H1 \rightarrow L1$, $H1 \rightarrow L2$, $L1 \rightarrow H1$ and $L2 \rightarrow H1$, to find the best values A_{L1} , A_{L2} and A_H , which maximize the minimum overall Q^2 among them. We performed such analysis and show the results in Fig. 4, for different HUB transmitted powers corresponding to $A_H = 3$ dB (Fig. 4(a)), 6 dB (Fig. 4(b)) and 9 dB (Fig. 4(c)). From these contour plots, we observe that there is a combination of A_{L1} and A_{L2} , for each A_H , that maximizes the overall achievable Q^2 . Moreover, this pair of values escalates with A_H . Roughly, these $\langle A_{L1}, A_{L2} \rangle$ pairs are: $\langle 3$ dB, 0 dB \rangle for $A_H = 3$ dB, $\langle 6$ dB, 3 dB \rangle for $A_H = 6$ dB and $\langle 9$ dB, 6 dB \rangle for $A_H = 9$ dB. Note that the maximum overall achievable Q^2 increases with the transmitted power of the HUB. These results indicate a multi-variable optimization problem, arising from the interplay of reflections, XT and intrinsic TRX noise, which is inherent to the P2MP single-fiber BiDi networks. In the experimental example presented here, only two LEAFs are considered. However, as long as the number of HUB to LEAF connections increases, the problem would become more complex, thus calling for more sophisticated optimization algorithms.

Conclusions

We report on the realization of P2MP single-fiber optical networks to support next-generation mobile transport, by using DSCM and single-laser coherent transceivers. We show that the performance of such networks is determined by the combined impact of reflections, receiver noise, and crosstalk, emphasizing the need for a multi-variable optimization approach to find the optimal power setting for each node. As network complexity increases with more HUB-to-LEAF connections, advanced and automated optimization algorithms will be crucial, presenting a promising area for future research.

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